

Review article

5S rRNA in Heteroptera – the current state of knowledge and future prospects

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Abstract. This paper provides a comprehensive overview of current research on 5S rRNA in true bugs (Heteroptera). It also highlights existing findings and potential possibilities for future investigation in this field.

Key words: Hemiptera, Cimicomorpha, Pentatomomorpha, ribosomal RNA, RNA secondary structure, RNA tertiary structure, molecular marker, phylogeny.

Introduction

Ribosomal RNAs, as components of eukaryotic ribosomes, are essential for protein synthesis and consist of four types: 5S rRNA, 18S rRNA, 5.8S rRNA, and 28S rRNA (e.g., Dinman 2009; Taylor et al. 2009; Ramakrishnan 2011; Wilson & Doudna Cate 2012; Anger et al. 2013; Gokhman & Kuznetsova 2024).

The smallest among these five structures is 5S rRNA (about 120 nucleotides), and it is the least frequently used element of ribosomal RNA in phylogenetic analyses because it is considered highly conserved across all eukaryotes (Szymański et al. 2003; Ciganda & Williams 2011; Vierna et al. 2013). Its secondary and tertiary structures have also rarely been analysed and predicted (McDougall & Nazar 1983; Ciganda & Williams 2011).

In true bugs (Hemiptera: Heteroptera), the most common ribosomal RNAs to be included in this type of analysis were 18S rRNA and 28S rRNA (Ouvrard et al. 2000; Li H.M. et al. 2005, 2006; Xie et al. 2005, 2008; Grazia et al. 2008; Li M. et al. 2012; Yu et al. 2013; Song et al. 2016; Wang et al. 2016; Wu et al. 2016, 2018; Lis J.A. et al. 2017; Weirauch et al. 2019; Bianchi et al. 2021; Roca-Cusachs et al. 2022; Lis B. et al. 2023; Lis J.A. 2023; Lis J.A. & Domagała 2024).

Although data for 5S rRNA (5S rDNA) have been published for various insect groups (Gillespie et al. 2006; Cabral-de-Mello 2011a, 2011b; Bueno et al. 2016; Volarić et al. 2024; Taha 2025), only one study referenced this gene in Heteroptera (Bardella & Cabral-de-Mello 2018). Sequences of the 5S rDNA were obtained for two species of the family Coreidae and deposited in GenBank (Bardella & Cabral-de-Mello 2018). Furthermore, we found that many 5S rRNA sequences for Hemiptera are also available in GenBank and other online databases, despite the lack of formal publications concerning these sequences.

For example, the RNACentral database (<https://rnacentral.org>) contains 3,064 5S rRNA sequences for Hemiptera, of which only 264 are sequences for Heteroptera.

Therefore, we have decided to summarise all data related to 5S rRNA (5S rDNA) in Heteroptera and to propose further research involving the 5S rDNA gene sequence and the structures of the ribosomal RNA (5S rRNA) encoded by it. All information was obtained from three databases: RNACentral (<http://rnacentral.org>), the 5S RNA Database (<http://combio.pl/rrna/>), and GenBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>).

The following list specifies, for each of the ten recorded Heteroptera species, their classification, the number of sequences available in each database, the lengths of these sequences, the presence of secondary structure information, and the prediction method used (where available within the respective database).

A list of species

Infraorder: Cimicomorpha

Family: Reduviidae

***Rhodnius prolixus* Stål, 1859**

RNA Central Database

Total: 49 sequences; reference genomes: 47 sequences.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 126 (1); 122 (4); 121 (3); 120 (6); 119 (23); 118 (1); 117 (3); 115 (2); 114 (1); 110 (1); 108 (2); 107 (1); 103 (1).

Secondary structure available: 46 sequences.

Secondary structure prediction: R2DT software.

5S RNA Database

No data.

GenBank

Total: 42 sequences (predicted).

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 122 (1); 121 (2); 120 (2); 119 (37).

Secondary structure: not available.

Family: Cimicidae

Cimex lectularius* Linnaeus, 1758*RNA Central Database**

Total: 21 sequences; reference genomes: 19 sequences.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 122 (3); 119 (11); 117 (1); 115 (2); 113 (1); 111 (1); 103 (2).

Secondary structure available: 20 sequences.

Secondary structure prediction: R2DT software.

5S RNA Database

Total: 3 sequences.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 122 (3).

Secondary structure available: 3 sequences.

GenBank

Total: 10 sequences (predicted).

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 119 (10).

Secondary structure: not available.

Family: Miridae

Apolygus lucorum* (Meyer-Dür, 1843)*RNA Central Database**

Total: 95 sequences; reference genomes: none.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 131 (1); 129 (1); 123 (3); 121 (2); 120 (6); 119 (39); 118 (12); 117 (2); 116 (3); 115 (2); 114 (2); 113 (1); 112 (1); 111 (2); 110 (2); 108 (2); 106 (3); 105 (2); 103 (1); 102 (2); 99 (1); 95 (1); 92 (1); 88 (1); 81 (1); 76 (1).

Secondary structure: not available.

5S RNA Database

No data.

GenBank

No data.

Nesidiocoris tenuis* (Reuter, 1895)*RNA Central Database**

Total: 8 sequences; reference genomes: none.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 119 (6); 82 (1); 75 (1).

Secondary structure: not available.

5S RNA Database

No data.

GenBank

No data.

Infraorder: Pentatomomorpha

Family: Lygaeidae

Oncopeltus fasciatus* (Dallas, 1852)*RNA Central Database**

Total: 10 sequences; reference genomes: none.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 122 (10)

Secondary structure available: 10 sequences.

Secondary structure prediction: R2DT software.

5S RNA Database

Total: 10 sequences.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 122 (10).

Secondary structure available: 10 sequences.

GenBank

No data.

Family: Pentatomidae

Halyomorpha halys* (Stål, 1855)*RNA Central Database**

Total: 3 sequences; reference genomes: 3 sequences.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 119 (3).

Secondary structure available: 3 sequences.

Secondary structure prediction: R2DT software.

5S RNA Database

No data.

GenBank

Total: 4 sequences (predicted).

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 119 (4).

Secondary structure: not available.

Nezara viridula* (Linnaeus, 1758)*RNA Central Database**

Total: 30 sequences; reference genomes: none.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 142 (1); 128 (1); 123 (1); 122 (2); 121 (1); 120 (4); 119 (15); 118 (2); 114 (1); 113 (1); 99 (1).

Secondary structure available: 1 sequence (119 nucleotides).

Secondary structure prediction: R2DT software.

5S RNA Database

No data.

GenBank

No data.

Piezodorus guildinii (Westwood, 1837)

RNA Central Database

Total: 1 sequence; reference genomes: none.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 122 (1).

Secondary structure available: 1 sequence.

Secondary structure prediction: R2DT software.

5S RNA Database

Total: 1 sequence.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 122 (1).

Secondary structure available: 1 sequence.

GenBank

No data.

Family: Coreidae

Chariesterus armatus (Thunberg, 1825)

RNA Central Database

No data

5S RNA Database

No data

GenBank

Total: 6 sequences.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 256 (1); 246 (1); 192 (1); 187 (1); 179 (1); 170 (1).

Note: Sequences of this species were published (Bardella & Cabral-de-Mello, 2018). However, each complete sequence includes 5S ribosomal RNA and the non-transcribed spacer (NTS).

Holhymenia histrio (Fabricius, 1803)

RNA Central Database

No data

5S RNA Database

No data

GenBank

Total: 5 sequences.

Number of nucleotides (number of sequences): 1168 (1); 849 (1); 735 (1); 703 (1); 666 (1).

Note: Sequences of this species were published (Bardella & Cabral-de-Mello, 2018). However, each complete sequence includes 5S ribosomal RNA and the non-transcribed spacer (NTS).

5S rRNA secondary structures prediction

In the analysed databases, information on the programme (R2DT; Sweeney et al., 2021) used to predict the secondary structure of 5S rRNA was available only in the RNACentral database (The RNACentral Consortium, 2019).

Secondary structures for some sequences are also provided in the 5S RNA Database (Szymanski et al., 2016). In this case, each record included data on the secondary structure, displayed as a diagram. Detailed information on the creation of these secondary structures is available in the 5S RNA Database under the 'Help' tab (refer to: '5S rRNA gene record' and 'Alignment').

The diagrams in Figure 1 (Fig. 1) illustrate the secondary structures of the 5S rRNA from the *Piezodorus guildinii* sequence (as an example) in both the RNACentral database and the 5S RNA Database. Additionally, we present (Fig. 2) the same sequence as secondary structures generated using RNAstructure version 6.3 (Reuter & Mathews 2010). This programme has been successfully used many times to predict secondary structures of rRNA in Heteroptera (Lis B. et al. 2023; Lis J.A. 2023; Lis J.A. & Domagała 2024).

5S rRNA tertiary structures prediction

Unfortunately, unlike the secondary structures of 5S rRNA, the tertiary structures of this ribosomal RNA have never been predicted in Heteroptera. Such data are absent from any publication or database.

Therefore, in this paper, we present the tertiary structures of the 5S rRNA from two species, *Piezodorus guildini* and *Nezara viridula*, as examples (Fig. 3). The predictions were made using RNAComposer (<http://rnacomposer.ibch.poznan.pl/>), a fully automated, accurate, and precise RNA structure modelling server (Popena et al. 2012; Biesiada et al. 2016; Kulkarni et al. 2023). The tertiary structure images were visualised using PyMol software version 2.4.0 (Schrodinger & DeLano 2020).

For comparison, we have also included a model of the tertiary structure of 5S rRNA from the halophilic archaeon *Haloarcula marismortui* (Volcani, 1940) (Oren et al. 1990; Fig. 3D). This is currently the most well-known model of 5S rRNA tertiary structure (Ban et al. 2000; Sun & Caetano-Anollés 2009).

Conclusions and future perspectives

1. Although 5S rRNA has been studied for decades, many questions about its secondary and tertiary structures remain unresolved.
2. This is especially significant for insects, particularly those in the suborder Heteroptera within the order Hemiptera.
3. A comparison of the number of 5S rRNA sequences available in databases and publications for the entire order Hemiptera and the suborder Heteroptera indi-

cates that further research into the 5S rRNA sequences of Heteroptera species is necessary.

4. Analysing the secondary and tertiary structures of 5S rRNA should include as many taxa as possible to detect differences at the species, genus, family, superfamily, and infraorder levels.

5. These analyses may assist in assessing the importance of 5S rRNA as a molecular marker in phylogenetic research on Hemiptera, particularly Heteroptera, across various taxonomic levels.

Fig. 1. Secondary structures of the 5S rRNA from the *Piezodorus guildinii* sequence in the RNACentral database (A–B) and the 5S RNA DB (C–D). The structures in B and C have been modified accordingly (B – according to the scheme used in the RNACentral database; C – according to the scheme used in the 5S RNA DB). Nomenclature of loops (LA, LB, LC, LD, LE) and helices (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5) follow Szymański et al. (2003).

Fig. 2. Secondary structures of the 5S rRNA from the *Piezodorus guildinii* sequence generated by RNAstructure ver. 6.3. A. predicted MaxExpect structure. B. predicted ProbKnot structure. C. predicted lowest free energy structure. D. comparison of all three structures predicted by RNAstructure ver. 6.3. The labels [a, b, c] correspond to the structures labelled A, B and C, respectively. The structures in figure D have been rotated according to the scheme presented in Sun & Caetano-Anollés (2009).

Fig. 3. Tertiary structures of the 5S rRNA. A. *Piezodorus guildini*. B. *Nezara viridula*. C. *Piezodorus guildini* and *Nezara viridula* in the same position, compared using PyMol (green – *Piezodorus guildini*, pink – *Nezara viridula*). D. halophilic archaeon *Haloarcula marismortui*.

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